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Biodiversity of the tunicate fauna at Nantucket and Muskeget Islands

Mary R. Carman, Biology Department, Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution

Abstract

Tunicates (Ascidiacea) are common benthic marine invertebrates that occur in New England and elsewhere from the intertidal zone to the deep sea. In the near shore, they are often the dominant fouling organism on anthropogenic and natural surfaces and are known to cause problems for shellfish aquaculturists. The tunicate fauna of Nantucket has not been previously documented. Our goal was to survey Nantucket and the nearby island of Muskeget for tunicates and to determine the biodiversity of the population for future comparisons. In July 2016, we surveyed Muskeget and found no tunicates. We also surveyed Nantucket in July 2016, and found 7 species of tunicates attached to anthropogenic substrates including boat hulls, floating dock sides, and ropes hanging off docks, and attached to natural substrates including bivalves, sponges, and eelgrass. When present, tunicate abundance or percent coverage ranged up to 50-75%. Of the 7 species observed on Nantucket, 5 are considered non-native species and 2 are considered native species. The Nantucket faunal composition, abundance, and substrates utilized are similar to other tunicate populations in New England.

Introduction

Tunicates (Ascidiacea) are common benthic marine invertebrates in the coastal habitats of New England (van Name 1945; Pederson 2005). Tunicates are filter feeders that live attached to various natural and anthropogenic substrates including boat hulls, docks, mooring lines, aquaculture gear, shellfish, boulders, other animals, and marine plants (Carman and Roscoe 2003; Bullard et al. 2007; Valentine et al. 2007) (Figure 1). Up until the 1960's, the Woods Hole, Cape Cod region tunicate fauna was dominated by native species (Zinn and Abbott 1964) that were minor members of fouling communities in harbors, but now the tunicate fauna is dominated by invasive species and tunicates are major members of fouling communities in harbors and elsewhere (Carman et al. 2007). The introduction of invasive tunicate species is attributed to ship ballast water and hull fouling and their local spread is attributed to recreational boat hulls and aquaculture transfers (Cohen and Carlton 1998). Further, the successful establishment of invasive tunicates in North American coastal waters may be linked to nitrogen pollution levels (Carman et al. 2007).

Non-native, invasive tunicates negatively impact eelgrass substrate (Wong and Vercaemer 2014) and eelgrass ecosystems (Carman and Grunden 2010), and negatively impact shellfish and shellfish aquaculture (Carman et al. 2010; Adams et al. 2011).

The tunicate population of Nantucket and Muskeget Islands had not been previously documented, and it likely includes a high proportion of invasive species. Tunicate populations documented elsewhere in southern New England include native and non-native species (Table 1).

Native species	Non-native species	Cryptogenic species
<i>Aplidium glabrum</i>	<i>Ascidella aspersa</i>	<i>Ciona intestinalis</i>
<i>Aplidium constellatum</i>	<i>Botryllus schlosseri</i>	
<i>Boltenia ovifera</i>	<i>Botrylloides violaceus</i>	
<i>Didemnum albidum</i>	<i>Clavelina lepadiformis</i>	
<i>Molgula manhattensis</i>	<i>Didemnum vexillum</i>	
<i>Perophora viridis</i>	<i>Diplosoma listerianum</i>	
	<i>Styela clava</i>	
	<i>Styela plicata</i>	

Table 1. Tunicate species that occur in southern New England

The goals and objectives of the study were to: 1) identify the composition and abundance of the tunicate fauna of Nantucket and Muskeget, 2) identify the substrate type that the tunicates are attached to, and 3) compare the fauna to other New England tunicate populations, all as baseline data for future comparisons. The goals and objectives of the study were conducted with the assistance of the Nantucket Biodiversity Initiative personnel. Given the proximity of Nantucket to Martha's Vineyard and mainland Massachusetts and the boat traffic to the area, I hypothesized that the tunicate fauna of Nantucket/Muskeget will be similar to Martha's Vineyard and Cape Cod, in southern New England, which are dominated by non-native tunicate species.

Alternatively, because of its isolation, it was possible that the Nantucket/Muskeget tunicate fauna would differ from tunicate faunas of southern New England, and be dominated by native species.

Methods and Study Sites

We conducted a rapid assessment survey (RAS) for tunicates at Nantucket and Muskeget by searching all manner of surfaces at harbors, marinas, aquaculture site, and eelgrass meadow with the assistance of Nantucket Biodiversity Initiative (NBI) personnel. We searched for tunicates by walking access, wading snorkeling and small boat use. Tunicates were identified to the species level to determine the biodiversity of tunicates. The relative abundance of tunicates was noted. The type of substrates utilized by the identified tunicate species, including anthropogenic and natural surfaces, as well as the geographic location of the tunicates, using GPS coordinates, were recorded. The results of the Nantucket and Muskeget tunicate surveys were compared to the documented tunicate faunas at nearby Martha's Vineyard and Cape Cod and elsewhere in southern New England. Voucher specimens of each species found were collected, preserved, and along with geo-reference information on where it was collected, submitted to NBI.

We also searched for the invasive jellyfish *Gonionemus vertens*, commonly associated with eelgrass meadows, in conjunction with the Annette Govindarajan (WHOI)-NBI 2016 funded project. In August 2016, Govindarajan in turn searched for tunicates during her surveys in Nantucket eelgrass habitat.

Results

On July 12, 2016, we surveyed the island of Muskeget. No artificial substrates were found; natural substrates, i.e. eelgrass beds on the north side of the island and a large interior pond, were searched by snorkeling. We did not find any tunicates, nor did we find the jellyfish *G. vertens*.

On July 19, we surveyed Nantucket and found tunicates (Table 2). We searched Nantucket Harbor on the north side of the island by small boat and found 7 species of tunicates on artificial and natural substrates. Specifically, we found *Botryllus schlosseri*, *Botrylloides violaceus*, *Diplosoma listerianum*, *Molgula manhattensis*, and *Styela clava* on a dingy boat hull and mooring line at N41° 16.936' and W70° 05.653' and specimens of each species were collected (Figure 1). At the Brant Point Shellfish Hatchery we found *Aplidium glabrum*, *Didemnum vexillum*, and *S. clava* attached to a rope hanging off the end of the dock at N41° 17.341' and W70° 05.459' and specimens of each species were collected (Figure 2). On the sides of the floating Town Dock we found *A. glabrum*, *B. schlosseri*, *B. violaceus*, *D. vexillum* (on dock sides and on blue mussels), and *S. clava* at N41° 16.913 and W70° 05.569 and specimens were collected (Figure 3). Tunicates were not found on dock pilings (treated wood; often with barnacles), several mooring balls, and the eelgrass bed on the north side of the harbor.

site name	latitude	longitude	species	substrate type
Nantucket Harbor	N41° 16.936'	W70° 05.653'	Bs, Bv, Dl, Mm, Sc	boat hull
Brant Point Shellfish Hatchery	N41° 17.341'	W70° 05.459'	Ag, Dv, Sc	dock rope
Town Dock	N41° 16.913'	W70° 05.569'	Ag, Bs, Bv, Dv	dock sides and blue mussels
Madaket Harbor	N41° 16.567'	W70° 11.724'	Mm	dock sides
Madaket Marine	N41° 16.755'	W70° 11.525'	Bs, Mm	dock rope
Walter S. Barrett Public Pier	N41° 16.486'	W70° 11.831'	Bs, Bv, Mm	boat hull and sponge
Jackson Point	N41° 16.291'	W70° 12.071'	Bs, Bv, Mm	eelgrass

Table 2. Tunicate species found at Nantucket in 2016; abbreviations: Ag=*Aplidium glabrum*, Bs=*Botryllus schlosseri*, Bv=*Botrylloides violaceus*, Dl=*Diplosoma listerianum*, Dv=*Didemnum vexillum*, Mm=*Molgula manhattensis*, Sc=*Styela clava*

Also on July 19, we searched 3 different dock areas in Madaket Harbor on the south side of the island by car and walking access and found 3 species of tunicates (that also occurred in Nantucket Harbor) on artificial substrates. Specifically, we found small *M. manhattensis* on dock sides at N41° 16.567 and W70° 11.724' and specimens were collected. At Madaket Marine we found small *B. schlosseri* and *M. manhattensis* attached to a rope hanging off the dock at N41° 16.755' and W70° 11.525 and specimens were collected. The small size of the tunicates in Madaket Harbor was probably due to the shallow water at the sites. At the Walter S. Barrett Public Pier we found *B. schlosseri*, *B. violaceus*, and *M. manhattensis* attached to a dingy boat hull and *B. schlosseri* on the native sponge *Halichondria panicea* attached to the boat hull (Figures 4, 5). We did not find *G. vertens* on Nantucket.

On August 17, Govindarajan observed *B. schlosseri*, *B. violaceus*, and *M. manhattensis* attached to native eelgrass *Zostera marina* at Jackson Point on Nantucket, at the east end of Massachusetts Avenue.

In summary, tunicates (n=7) were found attached to anthropogenic substrates including boat hulls, floating dock sides, and ropes hanging off docks, and attached to natural substrates including bivalves, sponges, and eelgrass. The tunicates identified belong to 3 orders: Aplousobranchia, Pleurogona, Stolidobranchia (see attached Appendices). When present, tunicate abundance or percent coverage ranged up to 50-75%.

Discussion

As hypothesized, the tunicate fauna of Nantucket is dominated by non-native, introduced, invasive species. Of the 7 species of tunicates found at Nantucket, 2 are considered native and 5 are considered non-native (Table 2). The possible exception to this, is the designation of *Botryllus schlosseri*. Yund et al. (2015) has suggested that *B. schlosseri* in New England may in fact be a cryptogenic species.

The presence of the egregious invasive tunicate *Didemnum vexillum* at the shellfish dock is alarming. This species is causing problems for aquaculture shellfishers in the US and Canada (Carman et al. 2010) and sea scallop fishermen at Georges Bank (Valentine et al. 2009).

While RAS are a standard method of determining the composition of a fauna at given locations (Pederson 2005), the method has its limitations. Settling plates may provide more data on recruitment successions, seasonal growth rates, and possibly additional species. Our goal was to document the fauna as a baseline for future comparisons.

The non-native species of tunicates found at Nantucket were probably introduced to the area via the great amount of boat traffic, both local and international.

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Figure 1. Dingy bottom in Nantucket Harbor; 5 species of tunicates, along with some bryozoans, cover the hull

Figure 2. Rope hanging off the dock at Brant Point Shellfish Hatchery; non-native tunicate *Didemnum vexillum* and native tunicate *Aplidium glabrum*, along with bryozoans

Figure 3. Nantucket Harbor Town Dock sides; non-native tunicates *Botryllus schlosseri* and *Botrylloides violaceus*

Figure 4. Dingy bottom at Madaket Harbor Walter S. Barrett Public Pier; small non-native tunicates *Botryllus schlosseri*, *Botrylloides violaceus*, and native tunicate *Molgula manhattensis*

Figure 5. Close-up of dingy at Public Pier (Fig. 4) of the native yellow sponge *Halichondria panicea* overgrown by the non-native tunicate *Botryllus schlosseri* (center of picture) surrounded by the native tunicate *Molgula manhattensis*

Appendices

Aplousobranchia

Pleurogona

Stolidobranchia